

***IN SITU* SYNTHESIS AND HIGH-TEMPERATURE PROPERTIES OF PARTICULATE TiB₂/Al COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT: Aluminum-based metal matrix composites (MMCs) with particulate TiB₂ reinforcement have been produced from Al-rich powder mixtures containing elemental Ti and B through a liquid-phase processing route and their mechanical behavior at high temperature (stiffness and creep) has been investigated. Unlike conventional powder processing using metal-ceramic powder mixtures, this processing technique synthesizes sub-micron sized TiB₂ particles *in situ* by chemical reactions. Examination by differential scanning calorimetry and X-ray diffraction revealed that on heating to 1000°C, Al₃Ti and AlB₂ are formed once Al starts melting ($3\text{Al} + \text{Ti} \rightarrow \text{Al}_3\text{Ti}$ and $\text{Al} + 2\text{B} \rightarrow \text{AlB}_2$) and these compounds subsequently decompose in the presence of liquid aluminum to produce TiB₂ ($\text{Al}_3\text{Ti} + \text{AlB}_2 \rightarrow \text{TiB}_2 + 4\text{Al}$). Thus, the net reaction formula should be $\text{Ti} + 2\text{B} + x\text{Al} \rightarrow \text{TiB}_2 + x\text{Al}$ with $x \geq 4$ for fully synthesizing the TiB₂/Al two-phase MMCs, the critical composition $x = 4$ (Al:B:Ti = 4:2:1) giving 27.9 vol.% TiB₂. To increase the reinforcement content beyond this limit, the addition of *ex situ* formed TiB₂ powder particles of 5 to 10 μm in size to the starting powder mixtures was effective. The use of coarse *ex situ* TiB₂ particles is also interesting in terms of microstructural control for producing a bimodal size distribution of TiB₂ particles. We therefore prepared three different 20 vol.% TiB₂/Al MMCs for mechanical testing: (1) 20 vol.% *in situ* TiB₂, (2) 10 vol.% *in situ* TiB₂ + 10 vol.% *ex situ* TiB₂ and (3) 20 vol.% *ex situ* TiB₂ (this was produced without reactive elements Ti and B). All of these had nearly full densities (~3.0 Mg/m³), the cylindrical form of green compacts being almost preserved after the liquid-phase processing. Using cylindrical dumbbell specimens (6 mm diameter × 30 mm length in gage portion), the temperature dependence of dynamic Young's modulus in the range from 25 to 400 °C and the creep behavior at 400 °C were examined for the three different MMCs. Results are discussed in light of our micromechanics-based models for predicting the dynamic (anelastic) modulus and the steady-state creep behavior in particulate MMCs (Acta Mater., **46**, 1209-1220 (1998); *ibid.* **48**, 891-901 (2000)). Briefly, the models emphasize the importance of particle size-dependent stress relaxation as a result of local mass flow (interfacial diffusion) around the reinforcing particles.

KEYWORDS: reactive sintering, particulate composites, aluminum, titanium diboride, stiffness, creep

INTRODUCTION

Reactive powder-based processing [1] has received considerable attention for making a new type of aluminum-based metal matrix composites (MMCs). Unlike conventional powder processing using particulate ceramic reinforcements produced *ex situ*, sub-micron sized fine TiB₂ particles can be synthesized *in situ* from Al-based powder mixtures containing elemental Ti and B, and/or their oxides TiO₂ and B₂O₃—the use of the oxide powders also produces fine Al₂O₃ particles as by-products [2-4]. The reinforcing ceramic particles thus produced may have 'clean' and thermodynamically stable interfaces. Since the *in situ* synthesis takes place in the liquid state of aluminum, the feasibility of near net-shape forming may also be a potential advantage. To date, however, the sequence of reactions in the Al-Ti-B system has not yet been fully understood so that blocky Al₃Ti, which is very brittle, often remains as an undesirable phase [5]. Furthermore, very limited investigation has been reported on their detailed mechanical characterization especially as high-temperature materials [6]. From the above, the work reported here was undertaken. First, we studied the reaction sequence for the TiB₂/Al MMCs synthesized from Al-Ti-B mixed elemental powders. Then, by incorporating coarse *ex situ*

TiB₂ particles in the liquid-phase processing of aluminum powder compacts with and without the reactive elements Ti and B, 20 vol.% TiB₂/Al MMCs with three different microstructures in terms of the size distribution of TiB₂ particles were produced and their mechanical behavior at elevated temperature was investigated with emphasis on the stiffness and creep properties.

FABRICATION OF COMPOSITES

1. *In Situ* Synthesis of TiB₂ Particles

For the synthesis of *in situ* TiB₂/Al MMCs from Al-Ti-B mixed elemental powder reactants, the net reaction may be described by the formula

Since TiB₂ is not directly formed from Ti and B by heating up to 1200 °C, Al plays a significant role, i.e., the presence of liquid-phase aluminum is requisite for the formation of TiB₂. As has been noted previously [5], the following reactions take place once Al starts melting:

This was confirmed also in our experiment by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and X-ray diffraction (XRD). **Figure 1** shows a set of DSC curves obtained for the composition $x = 6.2$, which corresponds to the formation of 20 vol.% *in situ* TiB₂ (the vol.% of TiB₂ implies a nominal one, simply calculated using the densities 2.7 Mg/m³ for Al and 4.5 Mg/m³ for TiB₂). On the first heating curve, a sharp exothermic peak appears just after the 660 °C endothermic peak due to the melting of Al, and a very broad exothermic peak follows. On the other hand, the DSC curves on cooling and reheating show only the solidification and remelting of Al, respectively.

Fig. 1. DSC curves for the composition $x = 6.3$ (Ti-2B-6.3Al), taken at a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C/min under an inert environment of Ar gas. The sample used is a fragmented piece of CIP-consolidated green compact made from elemental powders Al (99.7% purity, 1-5 μm), Ti (99.5% purity, <44 μm) and B (99.5% purity, <44 μm). A Fritsch P-6 planetary ball mill was employed

Results of XRD analysis are shown in **Fig. 2**. At 700 °C in between the two exothermic peaks, both AlB₂ and Al₃Ti were identified, as shown in Fig. 2 (a). Thus, it is evident that reactions (2) and (3) commence almost simultaneously. However, reaction (3) will be still in progress at 700 °C because diffraction peaks from Ti can be seen in Fig. 2 (a). Also, from the XRD pattern shown in Fig. 2 (b), it can be seen that all reactions have ceased at 1000 °C. These observations suggest that the two compounds AlB₂ and Al₃Ti should decompose, forming TiB₂ and liquid Al:

To confirm this reaction directly, a green compact

of $\text{AlB}_2\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ compound powder mixture with the equi-molar composition was prepared using AlB_2 (99% purity, $<44\ \mu\text{m}$) and Al_3Ti ($<44\ \mu\text{m}$) powders. The Al_3Ti powder was made in our laboratory by argon arc-melting, crushing and sieving from Al (99.7% purity) and Ti (99.5% purity) mixed powder compacts of the stoichiometric composition. Results of DSC experiment for this compound mixture are shown in **Fig. 3**. As can be clearly seen, a broad exothermic peak appears in

the range from 920 to 1030 °C on the first heating curve while the curves on cooling and reheating are essentially the same as those in Fig. 1. It was confirmed by XRD that the reactants AlB_2 and Al_3Ti remain unchanged below 900 °C and the products after the first heating/cooling run are TiB_2 and Al. Thus, reaction (4) can actually take place. Likewise, the broad peak observed in Fig. 1 for the mixed elemental powder reactants will be ascribed to reaction (4). The fact that the temperature range of the broad peak is variable can be explained in terms of the amount of liquid aluminum present. According to the Al-B binary phase diagram, AlB_2 decomposes at 975 °C accompanying an Al-rich liquid with a small amount of B. The liquid thus formed is very likely to assist reaction (4) in the case of $\text{AlB}_2\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ compound reactants (Fig. 3). As for the elemental reactants, on the other hand, a significant amount of liquid aluminum is present at 700 °C, as inferred from Fig. 2(a), so that reaction (4) can proceed at lower temperatures.

The reaction sequence described above implies that for the synthesis of TiB_2/Al two-phase MMCs by heating up to 1000 °C, the reactant composition $x\text{Al-Ti-2B}$ must be $x \geq 4$. In **Fig. 4**, the critical composition $x = 4$ (4Al-Ti-2B), giving 27.9 vol.% TiB_2 , is indicated by point P in the Al-Ti-B compositional triangle. A broken line with arrows indicates the compositional range $x \geq 4$. With attention confined to the field defined by Al-B- $\text{TiB}_2\text{-Al}_3\text{Ti}$ quadrilateral, some important aspects of equilibrium phase constitution can be drawn from this diagram, provided that no stable ternary compounds exist within the field concerned. For example, the state of coexisting three phases Al, TiB_2 and Al_3Ti in final products, which has often been observed [1-3, 5], is obviously not in equilibrium; the unstable Al_3Ti should then be accompanied by an AlB_{12} . If Al_3Ti in the three phases exists as a really stable phase, it will be deviated toward the Ti-rich side, i.e. the left-hand side of the Al- TiB_2 line in Fig. 4. For the reactants in which Al content is lower than the critical composition, i.e., on the P- TiB_2 line segment, reactions (2) and (3) can not proceed any longer when Al is consumed, and excess Ti and B are left. Subsequent heating causes reaction (4) to take place and liquid aluminum thus generated may again react with the excess Ti and B. Considering the broadness of DSC peak due to reaction (4), however, such sluggish reactions leading to TiB_2 will virtually terminate in the usual processing before the equilibrium state is attained. In fact, we tried to make 40 vol.% *in situ* TiB_2/Al MMCs under the processing condition described later, but the two-phase microstructure was unable to be obtained.

2. Particle Size-Controlled Microstructures

As shown above, the reactive powder processing can produce *in situ* TiB_2 particles of up to 27.9 vol.% in aluminum matrix without any coexisting intermediate phases. A possible way of increasing the reinforcement content beyond this limit is simply to add *ex situ* TiB_2 powder particles to the elemental powder mixtures. The size of *ex situ* particles is typically of the order of microns to tens of microns, so that the resulting MMCs will have microstructures characterized by a bimodal size distribution of fine *in situ* and coarse *ex situ* particles. Our composites were produced in the following way.

Fig. 4. Compositional triangle showing the critical composition P (4Al-Ti-2B) for *in situ* synthesis of TiB_2/Al two-phase MMCs.

Commercially available high-purity elemental powders, already mentioned in the caption of Fig.1, were blended in an alumina pot containing alumina balls and methanol using a Fritsch planetary ball mill, and then consolidated by cold isostatic pressing at 500 MPa. Cylindrical green compacts, typically 12 mm diameter \times 80 mm length, were heated up to 1000 °C at 4 °C/min and held there for 30 min in an argon-flow tube furnace. Cooling was controlled at two different rates, first at 4 °C/min to 700 °C and then at 0.33 °C/min for uniform solidification of the melt to avoid internal cavitation. In the fabrication of composites with *in situ* plus *ex situ* particles, TiB₂ powder of 325 mesh ($< 44 \mu\text{m}$) was added before ball milling. Furthermore, we tried to make composites with only *ex situ* TiB₂ particles without reactive elements Ti and B in the same processing route. Surprisingly, this was also successful. Thus, we prepared three different 20 vol.% TiB₂/Al MMCs for mechanical testing: (1) all *in situ* TiB₂ (20IN), (2) 10 vol.% *in situ* + 10 vol.% *ex situ* TiB₂ (10IN+10EX) and (3) all *ex situ* TiB₂ (20EX). In all of these, around 98 % of the ideal density (3.06 Mg/m^3) was attained.

Figure 5 shows SEM micrographs taken from a sample of 20 vol.% *in situ* TiB₂/Al MMC at different magnifications. It can be seen that almost all particles have sizes smaller than 1 μm and exist either individually or in the form of agglomerates. While most particles exhibit rounded appearance, some faceted ones can also be seen. Thus, individual particles are very likely to be formed as single crystals. Results of SEM observation for the *in situ* plus *ex situ* TiB₂/Al MMC are shown in **Fig. 6**. Here, the low-magnification micrograph, (a), shows the distribution of coarse *ex situ* particles, and coexisting fine *in situ* particles become visible at higher magnifications, as shown in (b). Note that initial *ex situ* TiB₂ powder particles are fragmented during planetary ball milling to sizes of, roughly, 5 to 10 μm . In many other SEM observations, there was no indication that *ex situ* particles influence the formation and/or distribution of *in situ* TiB₂ in such a way that they give preferential nucleation sites and make their own growth during the *in situ* TiB₂ synthesis. As for the 20 vol.% *ex situ* TiB₂/Al MMC, results are similar to Fig. 6 (a) except that the particle population becomes twice.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs showing a typical microstructure of 20 vol.% *in situ* TiB₂/Al MMC.

Fig. 6. SEM micrographs of 10 vol.% *in situ* plus 10 vol.% *ex situ* TiB₂/Al MMC.

MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION

There are many attractive features of particulate MMCs for engineering applications, including stiffness or specific stiffness enhancement, increased strength retention and creep resistance at elevated temperature, increased wear resistance, lowering thermal expansion, etc. Here we address the stiffness and creep properties. Emphasis will be placed on a mechanism of diffusion-controlled stress relaxation whereby the load-bearing capability of reinforcing particles is reduced, depending on the size of the particles.

1. High-Temperature Load-Bearing Capacity of Particulate Reinforcement

Introducing plastically nondeformable, thermally stable, ceramic particles with very high elastic modulus into a ductile metal matrix with much lower modulus is the basis for particulate MMC design. Upon loading, such particles carry a greater stress than the matrix, provided the particles are perfectly bonded to the matrix, i.e. no relative displacement occurs across the particle-matrix interface. At high temperature, however, the stress in the particles tends to be lowered in magnitude by a diffusion-controlled mechanism, as explained below.

Figure 7 illustrates an unreinforced matrix (a) before and (b) after the application of tensile stress. A circle in (a) defines a spherical domain which is to be replaced with a reinforcing particle. Under the tensile load, this domain becomes a uniformly elongated spheroid, as shown in (b). The deformation concerned is not only purely elastic but can include an *incompressible* inelastic strain due to plasticity or creep. In either case, it should be noted that the domain also changes its volume only elastically because a tensile stress σ causes an elastic dilatation of $\sigma/(3K)$, where K is the bulk modulus (of the elastically isotropic matrix). Now imagine the replacement of that domain with the spherical reinforcing nondeformable by plasticity and creep. Under the elongated shape but, considering a large difference in modulus, the particle will be a slightly elongated ellipse defining the particle circle in (b); then, the mesh drawn in (b) must illustrate an *unrelaxed* mechanical state where the particle exerts a maximal reinforcing effect.

Fig. 7. Drawings illustrative of the relaxation due to directional mass flow by diffusion along the particle-matrix interface under tensile loading. Mass flows from around the equator to around the poles of the particle.

The unrelaxed state can be *relaxed* if some *extra mass* of the matrix is removed from around the “equator” to around the “poles” of the particle in such a way that the ellipse in (b) gradually changes its shape toward the dotted circle, keeping elliptic configuration. Such local mass flow around the particle will take place at high temperature by diffusion of atoms (constituting the matrix) along the particle-matrix interface. In other words, excess vacancies to be present in the upper and lower near-pole matrix portions under hydrostatic tension will migrate toward the excess-atom, near-equator, matrix portion under hydrostatic compression. The stress-directed interfacial diffusion continues until the *gradient* in hydrostatic component of stress does not remain any longer throughout the matrix, i.e., the particle-matrix interface becomes a spherical shape. However, considering the elastic dilatation $\sigma/(3K)$ mentioned above, the location of this spherical interface must be drawn outside the dotted circle in (b). That is, if the interface is imagined to be debonded, then the resulting inner surface of the matrix must move outward while the particle is exactly delineated by the dotted circle. Hence, in the fully relaxed state, the particle should be subjected to a uniform hydrostatic tension. It should be noted that the interfacial diffusion-controlled relaxation described above is a strongly particle size-dependent rate process.

2. Temperature Dependence of Stiffness

The term “stiffness” usually means elastic modulus which is weakly temperature-dependent but essentially time-independent. At high temperature, however, stiffness becomes time-dependent and shows strong temperature dependence under certain conditions. This is due to *anelasticity*, which involves a rate process to relax a purely elastic state. For such stiffness, therefore, the term “dynamic modulus” will be used. In our experiment, we measured dynamic Young’s modulus in cyclic tension-compression loading at a very low frequency of 0.1 Hz using cylindrical dumbbell specimens of 30 mm length \times 6mm diameter in gage portion. Details of the measurement can be seen elsewhere [7]. Briefly, the change in gage length during cyclic loading, the resulting strain amplitude not exceeding 1×10^{-4} , was measured by scanning laser extensometry and the dynamic modulus was obtained via real-time digital data processing using a frequency response analyzer (FRA5020, NF Electronic Instruments). Results are shown in **Fig.8**, where the dynamic Young’s modulus is plotted against the test temperature for three different 20 vol.% TiB_2/Al MMCs, together with our previous data for unreinforced aluminum [7] for comparison. As can be clearly seen, the modulus is significantly increased by 20 vol.% TiB_2 particulate reinforcement with an increment of 40 GPa at room temperature and this enhanced modulus is essentially preserved in the range showing the ordinary linear temperature dependence. At higher temperatures, it is seen that the modulus markedly decreases in a nonlinear manner, which is a consequence of anelastic relaxation. While this must involve the

Fig. 8. Temperature dependence of dynamic Young’s modulus measured in cyclic tension-compression loading at a frequency of 0.1 Hz. Dotted straight lines represent the ordinary linear temperature dependence of modulus; the departure from there is due to the relaxation by stress-directed interfacial diffusion around the reinforcing particles and also by grain-boundary sliding in the matrix.

], the particle size-dependent relaxation discussed lower temperature side. Note that a characteristic proportional to d_p^3/D_b , where D_b is the boundary diffusivity and d_p is the particle diameter [7]. Hence, the smaller the particle size is, the faster the relaxation takes place at a given temperature and a given frequency. The stiffness lowering shown above will be an important consideration for high-temperature application of particulate MMCs especially under a long-term quasi-static loading condition.

3. Creep Behavior

Creep of aluminum-based particulate-reinforced MMCs, with *ex situ* SiC particles in particular, has been studied extensively. As long as a standard expression of power-law creep, $\dot{\epsilon} \propto \sigma^n \exp(-Q/RT)$, is assumed in the analysis of experimental creep data, anomalously large values of the stress exponent n and activation energy Q are usually observed. Hence, it is very common that the data is analyzed on the basis of a modified expression, $\dot{\epsilon} \propto (\sigma - \sigma_0)^n \exp(-Q/RT)$, where a threshold stress σ_0 is introduced. While the resulting n and Q values become much closer to those of the matrix, the expression above is never acceptable as a steady-state creep equation for MMCs because the applied stress σ itself is obviously not the stress which drives creep of the matrix. It is essential to consider the effect of load transfer, or *stress partitioning*, between the constituents in MMCs. A new approach to the analysis of steady-state creep data for particulate MMCs has been proposed [8], which is based on a micromechanical model of *coupled* flow [9]. Below, we first present our creep data for 20 vol.% TiB₂/Al MMCs and then discuss how to analyze them via the coupled flow model. The importance of interfacial diffusion-controlled relaxation will again be emphasized.

Using the same experimental setup and test-piece geometry as those used for the measurement of dynamic Young's modulus, constant-load creep testing in tension was done at 400°C. The specimen elongation, measured by scanning laser extensometry, was recorded at a time interval of 0.1 s. From the creep curves thus obtained, the steady-state creep rate or, in some cases, the minimum creep rate was carefully determined. Results are shown in Fig. 9, where the creep rate is plotted against the

Fig. 9. Log-log plot of the steady-state or minimum creep rate against the applied tensile stress, showing the presence of a threshold stress for creep that depends on the interparticle spacing.

figure, the encircled two data points with others are the steady-state ones; the meaning fitting lines, if drawn on this diagram, give lines are drawn instead—not fitting lines; they are obtained from calculations based on the coupled flow model, as explained below. First of all, it should be realized that deformation by matrix creep only, never attains the steady state. As creep proceeds over the entire matrix, an internal stress that suppresses further creeping, namely a *back stress*, develops due to piled-up dislocations around the particles. This is, therefore, a hardening process. For deformation to proceed in the steady state, some softening process must take place simultaneously. Hence, the interfacial diffusion-controlled relaxation will participate in the creep process of particulate MMCs. Our coupled flow model begins with the following two rate equations, one describing the matrix creep and the other, the relaxation by diffusion around the particles:

$$\dot{\epsilon}_p = A_\alpha \frac{\mu_m b D_v}{kT} \left(\frac{\sigma_m - \sigma_{m0}}{\mu_m} \right)^n \equiv \alpha (\sigma_m - \sigma_{m0})^n \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_a = A_\beta \frac{\delta_b D_b \Omega}{a_p^3 kT} \sigma_{p1} \equiv \beta \sigma_p \quad (6)$$

Here, σ_m and σ_p are the volume-averaged stresses in the matrix and particles, satisfying $\sigma = (1-f)\sigma_m + f\sigma_p$, where σ is the applied stress and f the particle volume fraction; σ_{m0} is the

threshold stress for matrix creep, d_p the particle diameter, and all other symbols have the usual meaning, see e.g. [10]. Note that the diffusional flow can be treated as if the particle deforms by Coble creep while the diffusing species are the matrix atoms. The steady state will be attained when the two processes of flow take place at the same rate, i.e. $\dot{\epsilon}_p = \dot{\epsilon}_d \equiv \dot{\epsilon}$, where $\dot{\epsilon}$ denotes the creep rate of the composite. Now we define a *stress-partitioning factor* ζ such that $\sigma_m - \sigma_{m0} = \zeta(\sigma - \sigma_0)$ with $\sigma_0 \equiv (1 - f)\sigma_{m0}$. Then,

$$\dot{\epsilon} = \alpha[\zeta(\sigma - \sigma_0)]^n \quad (7)$$

which describes the steady-state creep of MMCs. The stress-partitioning factor ζ is determined by solving $\zeta^n + M_\sigma[\zeta - (1 - f)^{-1}] = 0$ with $M_\sigma \equiv (1 - f)(\beta / \beta_0)(\sigma - \sigma_0)^{1-n}$. Note that this ζ depends on the applied stress σ as well as the temperature T . Hence, the creep equation above, (7), should give a curved line on the usual $\log \dot{\epsilon} - \log \sigma$ diagram. The coupled flow model shown above can be readily extended to the case where the reinforcing particles of different diameters d_{pi} ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) are distributed at volume fractions f_i . In this case, a characteristic particle diameter d_p , defined by $d_p \equiv \sqrt[3]{\sum_i p_i d_{pi}^3}$ with $p_i \equiv f_i / f$, can be used in (6). The three curved lines drawn in Fig. 9 are those calculated in the manner described above, using the physical property data listed in the literature [10]. The *in situ* and *ex situ* TiB₂ particles are treated simply by making two size groupings, 0.5 μm and 10 μm in average diameter, and the threshold stress σ_{m0} for matrix creep is calculated from $\sigma_{m0} \approx \mu_m b / \lambda$ with appropriate values of the interparticle spacing λ . As can be seen from Fig. 9, the calculations by the coupled flow model are in excellent agreement with experimental results, except for the two data points encircled. This deviation of data points, however, is due to damage such as interface debonding and/or particle cracking induced during the creep process, as was suggested in a theoretical analysis [9] and experimentally verified in an *ex situ* SiC/6061 Al MMC [8]. Note that such damage will occur more easily in larger particles because they are less relaxed by diffusional flow. In fact, the deviation occurs at a lower applied stress in 20EX than in 10IN+10EX while no deviation is seen in 20IN. Once damage takes place in the transient creep stage, the accelerated creep stage immediately follows. Hence, the steady state is never observed. Finally, it should be realized that reducing the particle size is very effective for raising the threshold stress level for creep while it naturally leads to very strong dependence of steady-state creep rate on applied stress. Thus, the optimal control of particle size distributions will be a point of interest in further research.

SUMMARY

Our on-going research on reactive liquid-phase powder processing and mechanical characterization of particulate TiB₂/Al MMCs has been reported in this paper. First, the reaction sequence for *in situ* TiB₂ synthesis from Al-Ti-B elemental powder mixtures is clarified by making a supplemental DSC/XRD examination of the Al₃Ti-AlB₂ compound reactants. An upper limit of 27.9 vol.% TiB₂ is found for producing the desired two-phase microstructure while the incorporation of *ex situ* TiB₂ particles makes it possible to increase the reinforcement content beyond this limit. Turning attention to the microstructural control with very fine *in situ* and coarse *ex situ* TiB₂ particles, we have examined the effect of particle size on high-temperature mechanical behavior of particulate MMCs using three different microstructure-controlled samples of 20 vol.% TiB₂/Al MMCs. The importance of diffusion-controlled relaxation is pointed out as a possible mechanism causing a significant reduction in the load-bearing capability of reinforcing particles at high temperature, and experimental data on dynamic Young's modulus and steady-state creep rate show clear evidence of this mechanism.

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